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Project Communications Strategy and Plan

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Abstract

This deliverable describes the communications strategy and plan for Month 1 to Month 36 of the GN5-IC1 project.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable sets out the communications and dissemination strategy and plan for Month 1 to Month 36 of the GN5-IC1 project.

Informed by the goals of GN5-IC1 as per the project's Description of Work (DoW), as well as those of its sister project GN5-1, this communications strategy and plan – drawn up by Work Package 1 Task 3 Communication and Dissemination (WP1 T3) in collaboration with Work Package 1 Task 1 Project Governance, Management and Coordination (WP1 T1) – addresses the project's different stakeholders and their requirements, outlining a plan of integrated, consistent communications that target these audiences through coordinated channels, with consistent messaging and impactful content.

GN5-IC1 communications will leverage the relationships already built and consolidated by the GÉANT organisation and via key projects such as GN4-3, GN4-3N and BELLA. Additionally, GN5-IC1 WP1 T1 and T3 will continuously collaborate with the Marcomms, Events and Policy Engagement Work Package (WP2) in GN5-1, and in particular with its T1 Communications and Design.

Further collaborations will be established with GN5-1 WP2 T4 Policy Engagement, a new task in the GÉANT series of projects that will facilitate the dialogue between GÉANT and policy makers and contribute to steering strategic discussions. GN5-IC1 communications activities will also be supported by the internal communications programme operated within the GN5-1 project by WP1 Project Management, specifically its weekly newsletter and annual project Symposium working conference.

Facilitated by a small and compact project team, internal collaboration within GN5-IC1 will cut across all work packages, with each task in WP2 taking care of different interconnected aspects of the project and WP1 working horizontally across teams to coordinate project activities and support internal communications.

The project's communications strategy will be aligned with GÉANT's International Strategy and will consider key topics of strategic relevance for the success of the GN5-IC1 project, such as European data sovereignty, security, interoperability with other world regions and resilience, and the project's impact in crucial scientific areas such as climate and environmental research, astronomy, physics, energy and fusion research.

The project's communications strategy, detailed in Section 2, informs a set of objectives which in turn form the basis of the communications plan, which is presented in Section 3. The key strategic and communication aspects that were considered when defining the communications plan include audiences, communications channels, messaging, content and stakeholder engagement. Based on this analysis, for each objective the plan sets out the actions to be taken to achieve it, the audience targeted by the actions, the channels used to reach the audiences and how often the actions are to be executed.

Central to the project's communications will be reinforcing the already established messaging that GÉANT and the pan-European GÉANT network are at the heart of global Research & Education Networking and the impact that Research & Education Networks have on global scientific collaboration.

GN5-IC1 Communications activities will be based on the same "twin track" approach to messaging adopted in GN5-1 and already successfully used in the GN4-3 and GN4-3N projects, involving two main communications streams, impactful and functional where 'impactful' communication uses a storytelling approach that addresses

the “WHY?” with engaging content that showcases the benefits of the project, and ‘functional’ communication addresses the “WHAT?”, highlighting facts, features and necessary information.

WP1 T1 and WP1 T3 will engage with all stakeholders, including Work Package Leaders and their Task Leaders, partners and participants in the GÉANT GN5-IC1 and GN5-1 projects, the European Commission, commercial providers, research infrastructures, etc.

WP1 T3 will use analytics and data reporting tools to monitor and measure the impact of the communications to ensure they are relevant, targeted, and cost-effective. The actions identified in the communications plan will be tracked on an ongoing basis and their success measured against the Key Performance Indicators set for the Task (WP1 T3), specifically relating to the project’s web and social media presence.

Progress towards the objectives and any issues identified will be monitored and reported on a regular basis to the Project Management Board and in the project management reports.

1 Introduction

The GN5-IC1 communications strategy and plan drawn up by WP1 T3 Communication and Dissemination in collaboration with WP1 T1 Project Governance, Management and Coordination aims to raise awareness of the project, its activities and ambitions, and highlight the impact these have on the European and global research and education communities.

This will be achieved through clear messaging and positioning statements, the production and publication of engaging content to address key stakeholders, and communication delivery through integrated, measurable, and collaborative channels.

This document first sets out the communications strategy (Section 2) devised by GN5-IC1 WP1 T3 in collaboration with GN5-IC1 WP1 T1 (Project Governance, Management and Coordination), taking into account the strategic direction set for the project and following on from the work carried out in the GN4-3 and GN4-3N projects.

Section 3 then presents the project communications plan, which is structured around a series of objectives based on the communications strategy. Details of the key communication aspects that were considered in devising the communications plan are also provided.

To track progress against the communications plan, key performance indicators (KPIs) have been agreed, which the WP1 T3 will monitor on a regular basis (Section 4).

The document concludes by summarising the key approaches required for the strategy and plan to succeed in meeting their objectives, and the areas where further growth and results are anticipated (Section 5).

2 Project Communications Strategy

The GN5-IC1 Description of Work (DoW) defines the project goals as follows:

GN5-IC1 sets out a new plan and implementation for the first phase of a new intercontinental connectivity investment programme, meeting the huge growth in network capacity demands and leading the network through a paradigm shift in the digital science and computational infrastructures in the next 10 to 15 years. It builds on the successful and relevant experience in planning and procuring and introducing into operation direct intercontinental links, such as BELLA S1, as well as a number of other existing bilateral and reciprocal arrangements for operational links negotiated with other intercontinental partners.

Additionally, the GN5-IC1 DoW includes the following primary objective:

The project objective is to ensure that sufficient network capacity is engineered and put in place through procurement and implementation of links during the project term and through setting a medium- to long-term roadmap for future investments beyond the project timeframe.

GN5-IC1 will pursue this objective, together with a number of supplementary objectives that span the duration of the project. Of these, the following are relevant to project communications:

- Extend the reach of network topology and capacity planning to a global scale, considering organic growth and demands from NRENs and research infrastructures delivered worldwide as shared resources, i.e., ITER, SKA, LHC and others.
- Co-ordinate network infrastructure investments in partnership with global NREN peers.
- Make choices and decisions in context with other relevant programmes, such as the EC's Digital Decade and NDICI, and DGs including the departments for International Partnerships (INTPA), Neighbourhood and Enlargement Negotiations (NEAR), Research and Innovation (RTD), Defence Industry and Space (DEFIS) and European External Action Service (EEAS) Regional Recovery Funds, and investments resulting from new apparatus e.g., the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) project, ITER and EuroHPC.

Informed by the above, the GN5-IC1 communications strategy aims to raise awareness of the project, its activities and ambitions, and highlight the impact these have on the European and global research and education communities. This should be done through clear messaging and positioning statements, the production and publication of engaging content to address key stakeholders, and communication delivery through integrated, measurable, and collaborative channels.

Communications and dissemination activities in GN5-IC1 will be carried out in continuity with the communications and dissemination strategy adopted by GÉANT over the various GÉANT projects – in particular the recently finished GN4-3 project – and building on the successful experience of the GN4-3N project, which is undertaking the refreshment and expansion of the backbone GÉANT network in Europe.

Additionally, GN5-IC1 WP1 T1 and T3 will continuously collaborate with the Marcomms, Events and Policy Engagement Work Package (WP2) of GN5-IC1's sister project GN5-1, and in particular with its T1 Communications and Design. The communications and dissemination strategies of the GN5-1 and GN5-IC1

projects will work in parallel, in a spirit of complementarity and continuous support aimed at reinforcing the overall impact of GÉANT's communications activities across all channels.

The GN5-IC1 project will make use of the effective communication channels established through the years by the successive GÉANT projects, benefiting from the lasting work of the Communications, Marketing and Events team in building and maintaining GÉANT's name and reputation. GÉANT's communication activities span a variety of communication channels, maximising the reach of its messages and content to a wide range of GÉANT stakeholder communities. Examples include the GÉANT website and services microsities (satellite websites in the GÉANT website ecosystem, the network.geant.org microsite being especially relevant to GN5-IC1), the CONNECT family of channels (website, newsletter and magazine), event participation, joint promotional campaigns with National Research and Education Networks (NRENs), and a social media approach that targets all stakeholders. Furthermore, the TNC event organised by GÉANT and partner NRENs routinely attracts over 800 attendees, with several thousand watching streamed content online.

GN5-IC1 communications will leverage the relationships already built and consolidated by the GÉANT organisation and via key projects such as GN4-3, GN4-3N and BELLA. Communication activities will also make use of additional channels and media outlets, such as the global 'In the Field' blog, the Science|Business weekly newsletter, news outlets specialised in Telecoms and networking, stakeholder joint collaborations, EC websites (CORDIS, websites of various DGs, EEAS, EU delegations in different countries), feature opportunities and social media, as well as of the communications channels of project partners and the RRENs and NRENs that are or will be connected to the GÉANT network. WP1 T3 will use analytics and data reporting tools to monitor/measure the impact of the communications to ensure they are relevant, targeted, and cost-effective.

Facilitated by a small and compact project team, internal collaboration will span across all GN5-IC1 Work Packages, with each task in WP2 taking care of different interconnected aspects of the project and with WP1 working horizontally across teams to coordinate project activities and ensure that progress, results and information are reported. In particular, WP1 T1 will support internal communications activities, by creating, maintaining and providing support for a coherent, easy-to-use, intuitive platform of IT tools and infrastructure to be used by project participants in their day-to-day work, including a project intranet, a shared repository, mailing lists and messaging systems for collaborative working.

GN5-IC1 communications activities will also be supported by the internal communications programme operated within the GN5-1 project by GN5-1 WP1 Project Management, and specifically by its weekly newsletter and annual project Symposium working conference.

GN5-IC1 WP1 T1 and T3 will also work closely with the GN5-1 WP3 User and Stakeholder Engagement team, to develop and implement communications plans that will enable dissemination and promotion, as well as allow dialogue with and feedback from the stakeholder groups. In particular, GN5-1 WP3 will be instrumental to encouraging and supporting utilisation of the enhanced intercontinental connectivity that will be delivered by the project through user support activities and international relations co-ordination with partners around the globe. Event participation will provide opportunities to engage with stakeholder groups and obtain their comments and input for consideration. A mixture of conventional and digital marketing materials will be deployed by GN5-IC1 WP1 T3, and news stories and channels will be carefully developed to ensure each stakeholder group is catered for in the most appropriate manner.

Finally, further collaborations will be established with GN5-1 WP2 T4 Policy Engagement, a new task in the GÉANT series of projects that will facilitate the dialogue between GÉANT and policy makers and contribute to steering strategic discussions. The support of this task will be crucial towards addressing matters of strategic relevance to the projects' communications and messaging and to make sure that the focus of GN5-IC1 communications is aligned with European policies.

WP1 T1 and T3 have identified a number of objectives and actions for the duration of the project (M1 – M36). These will be accomplished by building on the “twin track” approach already employed in GÉANT projects (notably GN4-3 and GN4-3N), an approach that separates “features” (functional) and “benefits” (impactful) to address different stakeholders with the most appropriate and compelling content and deliver this through targeted channels.

The project’s communications strategy will be aligned with the GÉANT International Strategy and will consider key topics of strategic relevance for the success of the GN5-IC1 project, such as European data sovereignty, security, and interoperability with other world regions, resilience, and the project’s impact in crucial scientific areas such as climate and environmental research, astronomy, physics, energy and fusion research.

As an integral part of their work, GN5-IC1 Task Leaders will contribute to the dissemination of the project’s results to relevant audiences. This will include:

- Presentations both to stakeholders in the R&E ecosystem as well as from the industry environment.
- Issuing news stories, usage studies and service documentation.
- E-infrastructure integration projects and suppliers through operational collaborations with, for example, international networking organisations.

In parallel and in accordance with the requirements of GN5-IC1 tenders, commercial providers collaborating with GÉANT in the GN5-IC1 project will also be required to develop communications, outreach, and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and exposure of tender awards, the delivery and implementation of their services and solutions and their collaboration with GÉANT.

A core role of WP1 T3 Communications and Dissemination will be to disseminate and promote the results and outputs of the project across the stakeholder communities through external and internal communications strategies and actions, helping to increase the success and adoption of services.

Additionally, WP1 T3 will aim to position GÉANT’s network and international connectivity within the global R&E networking community and scientific communities; to promote the value of NREs and RENs in the global R&E environment, for the ultimate benefit of a strengthened global R&E community; and to demonstrate tangible benefits of GÉANT’s intercontinental connectivity for the EU and its partners across Europe and internationally, as well as research communities.

The project communications strategy informs the communications plan, which is detailed in the next section.

3 Project Communications Plan

Focusing on a set of objectives informed by the strategy outlined in Section 2, the GN5-IC1 communications plan defines how and which information should be disseminated to meet the project objectives by answering the following questions:

- What type of information needs to be disseminated?
- Which communication channels should be used?
- Who does it need to be delivered to?
- When should it be delivered?

Section 3.1 below discusses the key communication aspects that have been taken into account to produce the communications plan. The plan itself is presented in Section 3.2.

3.1 Strategic Considerations

In putting together this communications and dissemination plan, WP1 T1 and WP1 T3 have followed the devised strategy by considering key communication aspects. These are the audiences that need to be addressed, which channels are appropriate for addressing the different audiences, what messaging approach will deliver the best results, how content is conveyed most effectively and how stakeholder engagement can be ensured. Each of these aspects is discussed below.

3.1.1 Audiences

The GN5-IC1 project addresses a diverse range of audiences (many of whom are stakeholders, see Section 3.1.4.1), including:

- a. GN5-IC1 Work Package Leaders (WPLs), Task Leaders (TLs), and project partners representing the Network Infrastructure Advisory Committee (NIAC).
- b. GÉANT Governance (GÉANT Board, GÉANT CEO and Executives).
- c. GN5-1 and GN4-3N Work Package Leaders (WPLs), Task Leaders (TLs), Coordinators and project participants.
- d. GÉANT Members (European NRENs, Representative Members, Associates).
- e. Institutions connected to GÉANT Members (universities, campuses, research institutes).
- f. Research Infrastructures and big science projects (CERN, ITER, SKA, etc.).
- g. Research communities.
- h. The European Commission.
- i. National governments.
- j. Global partners – non-European NRENs, RRENs.
- k. Industry – potential and existing suppliers, etc.

- I. Special Interest Groups (SIGs) and Task Forces (TFs) and global R&E network communities as the GNA-G (Global Network Advancement Group).
- m. The public.

These audiences have diverse interests and requirements for information and exhibit varying levels of engagement, and will often get their information from different communication channels.

3.1.2 Channels

Reaching the project audiences requires a range of communication channels that cater for different types of content and consumption.

The project will use different channels for different purposes. These channels include:

- Web presence
 1. NETWORK.geant.org (Primary)
 2. GEANT.org
 3. CONNECT.geant.org
 4. IMPACT.geant.org
 5. RESOURCES.geant.org
 6. MAP.geant.org
- Weekly newsletters
 7. GÉANT Project Office news from the Project Management Office (PMO) for GN5-1 and GN5-IC1 project participants
 8. CONNECT weekly newsletter subscribed to by a wide range of audiences.
- Magazine
 9. CONNECT Magazine.
- Social presence
 10. Social media:
 - Twitter
 - Facebook
 - LinkedIn
 - YouTube
 - Instagram
 - Mastodon
- Events:
 11. Internal meetings and Community meetings (e.g. NIAC Meetings, Global Network Advancement Group (GNA-G) meetings, Special Interest Group on Next Generation Networking (SIG-NGN) meetings, Special Interest Group on Marketing and Communications (SIG-Marcomms) meetings).
 12. Public events (e.g. TNC, industry events, EC events, international partner events).

Throughout GN4-3 and GN4-3N, significant progress was made in improving the project's communication channels, delivering several new websites for specific audiences, tailoring content for the increasing use of social

media, and growing GÉANT audiences. Together with GN5-1, GN5-IC1 will make use of these improved channels and broadened audience to achieve greater impact and efficiency.

Table 3.1 below summarises the audiences (see 3.1.1) and approach for each channel.

#	Channel	Audiences	Approach
1.	NETWORK.geant.org	All	The GÉANT Network site hosts the main page on the GN5-IC1 project, including all information around the project, news and interviews, links to resources and materials. Additionally, it showcases the pan-European GÉANT network and the ambitious GN4-3N project working on its upgrade and refresh. The site is for a potentially diverse group of audiences.
2.	GEANT.org	All	As the default entry point for all GÉANT audiences, this site aims to provide a high-level overview of all activities – for a potentially diverse group of audiences. It also includes a section on projects, which will host general information around the GN5-IC1 project.
3.	CONNECT.geant.org	All	This website is the primary source of news, articles and all timely content related to the GÉANT community. As part of its continuous stream of information, it will host regular updates and insights about the GN5-IC1 project, to be then distributed to other GÉANT websites and channels. It caters for a broad and diverse audience.
4.	IMPACT.geant.org	b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, l, m	This site is intended primarily for audiences who know little about GÉANT or its services, and as such content is written in non-technical language to highlight the societal impact of the project.
5.	RESOURCES.geant.org	All	The GÉANT Resources website brings together a growing range of documents and materials to support our members and partners. It will host GN5-IC1 Project Deliverables, White Papers, visual maps and collaterals.
6.	MAP.geant.org	All	Home to the interactive map of GÉANT Connectivity. To be progressed via the GN5-IC1 project
7.	PMO newsletter	a, b, c, h	This is targeted at all project participants and the EC Project Officer.
8.	CONNECT newsletter	All	By incorporating content from the CONNECT.geant.org site it can be assumed that the newsletter audience is the same as the website. However, the audience can be analysed closely by the subscriber details.
9.	CONNECT magazine	All	The magazine is compiled and written so as to appeal to all audiences, with a tone and language that addresses different groups individually.
10.	Social media	All	By its very nature, social media potentially covers all audiences. However, different social media present their own specificities and will help us to target specific

#	Channel	Audiences	Approach
			audiences. Of particular relevance for this project will be LinkedIn, followed by Twitter.
11.	Internal meetings and Community meetings	a, b, c, d, f, j, l	Internal meetings and community meetings include the Project Management Convention and Symposium, but also Special Interest Group / Task Force (SIG/TF) meetings, etc.
12.	Public events	All	External events will vary in their audience focus and need to be addressed individually. For example, TNC is focused on European and non-European NRENs, RRENs, EC, and industry. However, other events will focus specifically on research communities, EC, national governments, industry and the broader public.

Table 3.1: Communication channels – audiences and approach

3.1.3 Messaging

A consistent and integrated approach to messaging helps ensure that the project and its activities are positioned correctly and seen to be supporting wider initiatives, as well as building trust with stakeholders. WP1 T3 will continue to work with the Project Management Office (PMO) and with Work Package Leaders and Task Leaders to develop project-wide messaging.

Central to the project’s communications will be reinforcing the already established messaging that GÉANT and the pan-European GÉANT network are at the heart of global Research & Education Networking and the impact that Research & Education Networks have on global scientific collaboration.

Topics of strategic relevance, such as digital sovereignty, security, interoperability with other world regions and resilience, as well as key initiatives such as EU Global Gateway programmes, will need to be taken into consideration throughout GN5-IC1 communications and messaging. Equally important will be to pay special attention to possible geopolitical concerns and being mindful of messaging on sensitive topics.

3.1.3.1 Twin Track Approach

GN5-IC1 Communications activities will be based on the same “twin track” approach to messaging (Figure 3.1) adopted by GN5-1, already used successfully in the GN4-3 and GN4-3N projects. This means GN5-IC1 communications will be addressed through two main streams, impactful and functional. All the project’s audiences, channels and content are included in these two groups.

- **Impactful:** a storytelling approach that addresses the “WHY?” with engaging content highlighting the benefits of the GN5-IC1 project for Research and Education communities. This may take the form of success stories, articles, videos, graphics, animations, social media campaigns, posters, infographics, and others, delivered through channels such as *CONNECT* magazine, the *CONNECT* website or the *IMPACT* website. For example, governments and funding bodies can read interviews or articles in *CONNECT* magazine, or success stories on the *IMPACT* website, which show the importance of the GÉANT community working with the global research community, or the impact of global scientific collaborations.
- **Functional:** an informational approach that addresses the “WHAT?”, highlighting facts, features and necessary information. For example, NRENs receive information and insights about specific network

developments through internal meetings or via the GN5-1 WP3 Partner Relations and Engagement Task, or published on the GEANT.org website in appropriate sections. The information will focus on the features and technology of the solutions implemented.

Figure 3.1: Twin track approach to messaging

3.1.4 Stakeholder Engagement

WP1 T1 and WP1 T3 will engage with all stakeholders, including Work Package Leaders and their Task Leaders, partners and participants in the GÉANT GN5-IC1 and GN5-1 project, the European Commission, commercial providers, research infrastructures, etc.

Ongoing engagement with stakeholders, through both established and new channels, will be essential to the achievement of objectives. The level of detail will also be modified in accordance with the reader.

3.1.4.1 Stakeholder Impact Analysis

Table 3.2 (below) lists the stakeholders of the GN5-IC1 project and their interests, with the aim of determining the impact they have on GN5-IC1 communications and dissemination. This integrated approach to understanding the stakeholders is useful to ensure effective communications.

Stakeholders	Interests	Estimated Impact	Estimated Priority
WPLs, TLs, Project participants (partners / NIAC)	<p>WPLs and TLs have a responsibility to disseminate their work and to engage with their audiences. WP1 T3 will work closely with them to ensure their communications needs are fully met and support the project's overall objectives.</p> <p>Other than GÉANT, project participation is limited to NIAC members. These will also serve as a point of contact with key NRENs in the GÉANT Association.</p>	Medium	2
European Commission	The EC requires the project to communicate its work and the resulting benefits to a wide range of audiences and needs to be kept up to date with developments and success stories. Therefore, the Task will work with the Project Officer to support their outreach efforts.	High	1
Industry / providers	As a requirement of GN5-IC1 tenders, commercial providers will need to collaborate with GÉANT on communications activities, by producing press releases, case studies and promoting joint activities via their channels.	High	1
European NRENs / GÉANT Members (national, representative, associate)	The work of GN5-IC1 will ultimately benefit European NRENs and their Research and Education communities. As such, it will be mutually beneficial to coordinate communications efforts with GÉANT member NRENs.	High	1
Global partners – non-European NRENs, RRENs.	GÉANT will work with its international partners are peers and coordinate all communications activities with each partner benefiting from network upgrades via GN5-IC1.	High	1
Research Infrastructures and big science projects (CERN, ITER, SKA).	The project will need to collaborate with research infrastructures and large scientific endeavours to highlight the impact of GN5-IC1 in support of global science.	High	1
National Governments.	The project will consider the possibility of joint communications activities with national	Low	3

Stakeholders	Interests	Estimated Impact	Estimated Priority
	governments of the countries benefitting from GN5-IC1 connectivity upgrades.		
The public.	It is not expected for the general public to benefit directly from GN5-IC1. However, we can foresee a broader resonance of GN5-IC1 actions due to the impact that the project will have on global R&E networking and on national and regional economies.	Low	3

Table 3.2: Stakeholder impact analysis

3.2 Communications Plan

Taking into consideration all the factors discussed in Section 3.1, the communications plan below details each objective, the actions to be taken to achieve it, the audience targeted by the actions, the channels used to reach the audiences and how often the actions are to be executed. The success of the actions defined in the plan is measured against the agreed key performance indicators (KPIs) described in Section 4. Progress towards the objectives and any issues identified will be monitored and reported on a regular basis to the Project Management Board and in the project management reports, and the plan adjusted accordingly where necessary.

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
Position and promote the GÉANT network and its international connectivity to European and global stakeholders.	Through the GN5-IC1 project, WP1 T1 and WP1 T3 will contribute to raising GÉANT's profile as the core organisation at the heart of global Research & Education Networking.	Support awareness of key topics with feature articles, interviews, and news items published and promoted in the most relevant channels.	• All	CONNECT magazine	Quarterly/every two quarters
		Promote the implementation and delivery of new routes with articles, graphic, infographics, videos/animations and interviews with GN5-1 key staff. Collaborate with Global partners at key points – e.g. equipment installation, new fibre routes coming online, etc. Collaborate with commercial suppliers to establish opportunities for joint promotion. Utilise most relevant social media channels for promotion – in particular LinkedIn, as demonstrated in GN4-3N.	• All	CONNECT channels	Monthly / Bi-monthly
			Social media	As needed / regularly	
			Workshops	As needed	
			Conferences	As needed	
			Events	As needed	
			External media (press)	As needed	

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
		Populate the NETWORK.geant.org website with a GN5-IC1 dedicated section, as the main source of information related to the project, its progress and developments, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 	NETWORK.geant.org website	N/A
Collaborate with NRENS in Europe, regional and national partners worldwide, big scientific collaborations, research infrastructures and commercial partners to maximise global reach.	GÉANT has a comprehensive range of channels. However, leveraging the reach of other stakeholders is important to maximise dissemination.	Contribute articles and success stories to the EC for publishing through their channels.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 	EC channels	As needed
		Contribute to In the Field Stories and promote this initiative throughout GÉANT channels.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 	In the Field website	Annually
		Invite contributed articles from global NRENS, RRENS and other partners for publishing in CONNECT channels.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 	CONNECT channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As needed (for online and newsletter) Annually (for magazine)
		Undertake joint press releases with suppliers where appropriate. Collaborate on joint announcements with user communities, NRENS and RRENS as required.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 	CONNECT channels Media (press)	As needed As needed

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
		Leverage media outlets as the Science Business weekly newsletter, and telecoms industry outlets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 	Media outlets websites Media outlets social media	As needed As needed
Collaborate and cooperate with regional projects, to show the value of global interconnectivity.		Cross-mention activities and projects to allow joint dissemination. Examples of relevant regional projects to take into consideration include (but are not limited to) AfricaConnect, EaPConnect and BELLA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 	Regional projects websites Media outlets social media	As needed As needed
Demonstrate the capabilities, value, and impact of GÉANT’s international reach and the existing global fabric of interconnected RENS and NRENS (GREN).	The Task should do this through all relevant channels, but in particular utilising two websites to demonstrate the impact of the GÉANT and R&E networks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IMPACT.geant.org (GÉANT owned) highlights how the project enables large 	Develop new case studies for the IMPACT site. These can focus on user communities or individual projects, or on NRENS/RRENS or e-infrastructure partners to highlight the value of the GÉANT community. Promote the featured articles, create supporting materials (such as gifs, short video interviews with representatives) for use on social media channels, in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All All 	IMPACT.geant.org CONNECT magazine CONNECT website	As needed Quarterly/every two quarters Quarterly

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
	research projects and supports research communities. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The In the Field Stories website, which can be contributed to by all NRENS. 	collaboration with the featured projects and organisations.		CONNECT newsletter	Quarterly
				Social media	As needed / regularly
		Contribute to In the Field Stories and promote this initiative throughout GÉANT channels.	• All	In the Field Stories website and social media	As needed
		Provide full communications, branding and design support for external events at which the GN5-IC1 project has a presence: TNC, community events, industry events and others as needed.	• ALL	External events	Ad hoc
Promote the GN5-IC1 project and its activities.		Produce project achievements sheets, ongoing web pages and banners for the GÉANT website.	• All	GÉANT channels; GÉANT website; EC and partner websites	M1-M36
		Publish news items, articles and interviews to highlight the project's capabilities and value and promote through all channels.	• All	GÉANT channels; GÉANT website; EC channels; third-party sites such as Science Business; and others as deemed relevant.	M1-M36

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
		Produce engaging content to promote all areas of the project. This may take the form of feature articles, animated content, graphics, etc. – for use across all channels.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 	GÉANT channels including social media, GÉANT websites, etc.	M1-M36
		Where needed, update branding guidelines and presentation templates for all partners and participants to use, to ensure consistent branding and practice by project participants.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a, b, c, d, f, h, j 	RESOURCES.geant.org website	As needed

Table 3.3: Communications plan

4 Key Performance Indicators

The success of the communications plan is measured against key performance indicators (KPIs).

The following KPIs have been set for WP1 T3 against which to measure the effectiveness of the actions:

- Web presence:
 - An average of >200 pageviews per month on the network.geant.org webpages dedicated to GN5-IC1 and international connectivity.
 - An average of >150 pageviews each on GN5-IC1 articles published on the CONNECT website.
 - GN5-IC1 project featured on the websites of at least eight other RRENS or NRENS.
- Social Media:
 - An average of >400 impressions and >30 engagements on Tweets and on Facebook posts dedicated to GN5-IC1.
 - An average of >800 impressions and >80 engagements on LinkedIn posts dedicated to GN5-IC1.

Use of the #IC1 hashtag will help to filter and monitor the performance of social media posts dedicated to the GN5-IC1 project and all connected activities.

A mini-dashboard is being set up to allow easy monthly reporting of the figures related to these KPIs and all the main measurable communication activities related to the GN5-IC1 project.

Figure 4.1: Example of mini reporting dashboard produced for GÉANT activities.

5 Conclusions

The GN5-IC1 project represents a paradigm shift in GÉANT's approach to intercontinental connectivity. This means communications and dissemination activities in GN5-IC1 will have to face challenges associated with the novel and innovative strategic aspects of the project. On the other hand, GN5-IC1 can rely on the consolidated communication approaches that have proved successful in previous GÉANT projects, notably GN4-3 and GN4-3N.

It is anticipated that the objectives and associated actions identified in this deliverable will bring clarity and purpose to the project's communication strategy and plan, thus providing the best possible support to the project's objectives.

The following approaches will be required to ensure the successful outcome of the planned actions:

- Close collaboration will be fundamental between all GN5-IC1 Work Packages and Tasks.
- Close collaboration will also be necessary with GN5-IC1's sister project GN5-1, and in particular with GN5-1 WP1 Project Management, GN5-1 WP2 Marcomms, Events and Policy Engagement and with GN5-1 WP3 User and Stakeholder Engagement.
- Engaging and appropriate content for diverse stakeholders will need to be created that can also be easily shared with and by project partners and by the main stakeholders. The established 'twin-track' approach that has proved effective in GN4-3 should continue to be followed, and a diverse range of content utilised to suit the digital landscape, and subsequent evolving behaviours of audiences.

Progress towards the GN5-IC1 communications and dissemination objectives will be monitored on a monthly basis and reported on at the Project Management Board meetings and in the periodic Project Management Reports. Adjustments to the plan will be made where necessary to ensure completion.

Glossary

DEFIS	Defence Industry and Space
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EEAS	European External Action Service
EuroHPC	European High-Performance Computing
FPA	Framework Partnership Agreement
GNA-G	Global Network Advancement Group
Horizon Europe	EU Research and Innovation programme
DG INTPA	DG for International Partnerships
DG RTD	DG for Research and Innovation
ITER	International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NEAR	Neighbourhood and Enlargement Negotiations
NIAC	Network Infrastructure Advisory Committee
NREN	National Research and Education Network
PMO	Project Management Office
RREN	Regional Research and Education Network
SIG	Special Interest Group
SIG-Marcomms	Special Interest Group on Marketing Communications
SIG-NGN	Special Interest Group on Next Generation Networking
SKA	Square Kilometre Array
T	Task
TF	Task Force
TL	Task Leader
TNC	The Networking Conference (formerly TERENA Networking Conference)
WP	Work Package
WP1	GN5-IC1 Work Package 1 Project Management
WP2	GN5-IC1 Work Package 2 Intercontinental Connectivity: Planning, Co-ordination, Procurement and Implementation
WPL	Work Package Leader